

Co-UDlabs

**Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research
Labs communities**

**D8.4. Report on hydrodynamic design for stormwater
detention ponds optimized for cost-efficient maintenance**

Date of delivery - 31/10/2023

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Starting date	01.05.2021
Duration	48 months
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Deliverable Information	
Deliverable number	D8.4
Work package number	8
Deliverable title	Report on hydrodynamic design for stormwater detention ponds optimized for cost-efficient maintenance
Lead beneficiary	Aalborg University
Authors	<p>Aalborg University (AaU): Jesper E. Nielsen Michael R. Rasmussen Rasmus Laursen Jacob B. Jensen Janni M. Nielsen</p> <p>University of A Coruña (UDC): Juan Naves García-Rendueles Luis Cea</p> <p>INSA Lyon (INSA): Gislain Lipeme-Kouyi</p>
Due date	31/10/2023
Actual submission date	31/10/2023
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

VERSION MANAGEMENT

Revision history and quality check			
Version	Name	Date	Comment
V 0.1	Jesper E. Nielsen (AaU)	21/08/2023	First draft
V 0.2	Jesper E. Nielsen (AaU)	21/09/2023	Internal Review
V 0.3	Juan Naves (UDC)	22/09/2023	Contributions from UDC
V 0.4	Luis Cea (UDC)	28/09/2023	Internal Review
V1.0	Luis Cea, Juan Naves, Andrea Ciambra (UDC)	26/10/2023	Final working draft

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF TABLES.....	5
LIST OF FIGURES	5
BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE CO-UDLABS PROJECT	7
LIST OF ACRONYMS	8
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
1. INTRODUCTION	10
2. THE EXPERIMENTAL SUDS FACILITY AT AAU	11
2.1. The concept and structure of the facility	11
2.1.1. The inlet structure.....	12
2.1.2. The main basin.....	13
2.1.3. The retention basin.....	14
2.1.4. The receiving stream	16
2.2. Instrumentation, data access and visualization	17
3. SEDIMENT TRANSPORT AND LOAD FROM THE CATCHMENT	19
3.1. Self-cleaning and sediment transport from the contributing stormwater catchment	19
3.2. Sediment load of total suspended solids under rainfall.....	24
3.2.1. Experimental setup.....	24
3.2.2. Recorded rainfall events and inflow to the facility.....	25
3.2.3. Total Suspended Solids (TSS) of the stormwater and evaluation of first flush effects.....	26
4. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE SETTLED SEDIMENT IN THE MAIN BASIN	31
4.1. Grain-size distribution and organic matter content of the sediment.....	31
4.1.1. Organic content of the sediment	34
4.2. Heavy metal concentration of the sediment.....	35
5. CFD MODELLING OF THE MAIN BASIN.....	38
5.1. Evaluation of the inlet section of the main basin.....	38
5.1.1. Model setup.....	39
5.1.2. Evaluating the hydrodynamic flow patterns of the inlet configurations.....	40
5.1.3. Evaluating the inlet configurations' influence on the residence time of the main basin	44
5.1.4. Bottom shear stress during basin filling	47
5.2. Evaluation of the outlet section of main basin	48
5.2.1. Bottom shear stress during emptying the basin.....	50
6. LSPIV INSTALLATION AND TEST AT THE EXPERIMENTAL SUDS FACILITY	52
6.1. Installation of LSPIV	52
6.2. Inlet test.....	54
6.3. Outlet test.....	54
6.4. LSPIV processing.....	55
6.5. Results.....	56
6.6. Summary	59
7. IMPROVE THE MANAGEMENT OF DETENTION PONDS	60
8. CONCLUSIONS AND CONTRIBUTION TOWARDS THE OBJECTIVES OF CO-UDLABS	61
9. REFERENCES	62

List of tables

Table 3.1: Shear stress and maximum particle sizes that can be transported at 10% of full capacity flow in the stormwater pipes of the system.....	23
Table 3.2: Characteristics of the recorded rainfall events.....	25
Table 4.1: Wavelengths applied for the ICP-analysis.	36
Table 4.2: Wavelengths applied for the ICP-analysis.	36

List of figures

Figure 2.1: Overview of the catchment and the AAU experimental SUDS facility in Northern Jutland, Denmark. ...	11
Figure 2.2: Schematic overview of the system.	12
Figure 2.3: Schematic sideview of the inlet structure, main basin, and pump system.	12
Figure 2.4: The inlet structure to the main basin. At the top of the image, the motorized valve towards the main basin can be seen. On the left, the manually controlled weir is visible, as well as the pipe entrance for the by-pass to the retention basin.....	13
Figure 2.5: The SUDS facility. Left image shows the inlet structure, main basin, and the small building with technical installations. Right image shows the main basin with the porous wall installed.....	14
Figure 2.6: The retention basin. Top: Situation map of the retention basin. Bottom: The retention basin pictured from north-east (left) and north-west (right).....	15
Figure 2.7: The receiving stream, Landbækken. Left: Situation map illustrating the location of the receiving stream relative to the SUDS facility. Right: The discharge point to the stream (top) and Landbækken where it runs under the road (bottom).....	16
Figure 2.8: Screen dump of the webpage visualizing the current state of the experimental SUDS facility.....	17
Figure 3.1: Estimated wall shear stress of stormwater drainage system in the contributing catchment.	21
Figure 3.2: Shields diagram. If the relationship between Shield's parameter and the critical boundary-Reynolds number is above the curve, the sediment is expected to be transported. Southard (2006).....	22
Figure 3.3: Sampling setup at the inlet structure. Left: sampling tube with nozzle. Right: The auto-sampler.....	25
Figure 3.4: Recorded rainfall events measured by the nearest meteorological tipping-bucket rain gauge approx. 1,200 m south of the facility.....	25
Figure 3.5: Inlet flow to the facility during the recorded events and the measured rain intensity during the event.	26
Figure 3.6: TSS samples on the filters after drying. The first sample taken is the upper left and the order of sampling goes from left to right.....	27
Figure 3.7: TSS concentration measurements during the two recorded events.....	27
Figure 3.8: Relative accumulated Mass-Volume curve for the two events.....	29
Figure 4.1: Sediments deposits at the main basin. Left: before the porous wall. Right: After the wall	32
Figure 4.2: Sample location for sediment samples. The first 9 samples are located before the porous wall	32
Figure 4.3: Grain-size distributions of samples from the first sampling campaign (5 months)	33
Figure 4.4: Comparison of grain-size distributions of samples from the two sampling campaigns.....	34
Figure 4.5: Organic matter content of the sampled sediment measured by loss of ignition after 48 hours burning at 550°C.	35

Figure 4.6: Sampling locations for the heavy metal analysis.....	35
Figure 4.7: Comparison of heavy metal concentrations in the main basin.....	37
Figure 5.1: Inlet configurations. (a) Porous wall. (b) Manifold. (c) Baffle and diverted jet.....	38
Figure 5.2: Velocity patterns of the reference without any inlet configuration. Top: horizontal plane of the basin 0.9 m above the bottom of the basin. Bottom: vertical plane through the centre line of the basin.	41
Figure 5.3: Particle trajectories seen from above for the reference without any inlet configuration.....	41
Figure 5.4: Velocity patterns of the porous wall configuration. Top: horizontal plane of the basin 0.9 m above the bottom of the basin. Bottom: vertical plane through the centre line of the basin.....	42
Figure 5.5: Particle trajectories seen from above for the porous wall configuration.	42
Figure 5.6: Velocity patterns of the Manifold configuration. Top: vertical plane through the centre of the inlet manifold. Middle: horizontal plane of the basin 0.9 m above the bottom of the basin. Bottom: vertical plane through the centre line of the basin.	43
Figure 5.7: Particle trajectories seen from above for the Manifold configuration.	43
Figure 5.8: Velocity patterns of the Baffle and diverted inlet jet configuration. Top: horizontal plane of the basin 0.9 m above the bottom of the basin. Bottom: vertical plane through the centre line of the basin.	44
Figure 5.9: Particle trajectories seen from above for the Manifold configuration.	44
Figure 5.10: Response curves of the evaluated inlet configurations. * Indicate the effective residence time, t_{50} ..	46
Figure 5.11: Residence time performance for the evaluated inlet configurations.	46
Figure 5.12: Simulated bottom shear stresses during filling to 0.7 m depth.	48
Figure 5.13: Perforated outlet pipe configuration.	49
Figure 5.14: Right: Simulated bottom shear stresses for the reference outlet at 2 cm water level. Left: Photo of the sediment at the facility.....	50
Figure 5.15: Simulated bottom shear stresses for the water level-based pump controlled outlet (left) and the Perforated outlet pipe outlet (Right), both at a water level of 2 cm.	51
Figure 6.1: Encapsulating the equipment protecting it from the elements.....	52
Figure 6.2: Installation of the equipment at the Experimental SUDS facility.....	53
Figure 6.3: Identifying and obtaining coordinate reference elements.	54
Figure 6.4: Recording the inlet.	54
Figure 6.6: Example of frame rectification, frame filtering, raw velocity data obtained, and final filtered velocity results for the inlet test.	56
Figure 6.7: Example of frame rectification, frame filtering, raw velocity data obtained, and final filtered velocity results for the inlet test.	57
Figure 6.8: Example of frame rectification, frame filtering, raw velocity data obtained and final filtered velocity results for the inlet test.	58

Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create a urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning/Full text
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
LSPIV	Large-Scale Particle Image Velocimetry
ppb	parts per billion
TSS	Total Suspended Solids
UDS	Urban Drainage Systems
VOF	Volume of Fluid

Executive summary

This document is Deliverable 8.4 of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626. This deliverable is an output from Task 8.3.1 of Work Package 8 "Improving resilience and sustainability in urban drainage solutions".

The AaU is the responsible and main author of this deliverable. The lead beneficiary of Work Package 8 is University of A Coruña.

The Deliverable is a report on the main activities and results obtained within Task 8.3, which was focused on the hydrodynamic design of storm water detention ponds optimized for a cost-efficient maintenance. The activities were mainly undertaken at the detention pond located at Aalborg University. The flow and sediment load coming into the pond from the drainage catchment was characterized experimentally for several rainfall events, as well as the grain-size distribution, the organic matter content and the heavy metal concentration of the sediments. The hydrodynamics of the detention pond were analyzed using both a numerical model and experimental observations. A 3D numerical model of the experimental facility was developed using the software Star-CCM+, in order to estimate the flow patterns and bottom shear stresses in the basin during its operation. At the same time the surface velocity patterns were characterized by means of Large Scale Particle Image Velocimetry (LSPIV). The installation of the cameras needed for LSPIV, as well as the analysis of the images recorded, were supported by UDC. As a result of the activities undertaken, valuable insights into the management of detention ponds were gained, which are applicable to both existing ponds and the planning of new ponds.

1. Introduction

In Urban drainage systems, stormwater detention plays a significant role in the treatment and controlled release of stormwater to receiving waters. Although separated stormwater typically contains fewer pollutants compared to stormwater from combined sewers, it still has the potential to contain various xenobiotics that originate from urban surface deposits (Hvitved-Jacobsen et al., 2010). These xenobiotics can have acute or long-term toxic effects on the aquatic organisms living in the receiving waters (Kong et al., 2005; Logan, 2007).

The benefits of stormwater detention ponds are twofold. First, they provide protection to the receiving waters by reducing the hydraulic load. Urban runoff often generates unnaturally high flows that can erode the receiving stream and destroy its natural habitats. Detention ponds attenuate these high flows, allowing a more controlled release of stormwater and mitigating the potential damage to the recipient. Secondly, stormwater detention ponds serve as a mechanism for trapping a significant portion of organic and inorganic particulates present in the stormwater. As stormwater flows into the pond, suspended solids, sediments, and other particulate matter settle out due to the reduced flow velocity. This process helps reduce the overall pollutant load entering the receiving waters, thus minimizing the potential adverse impacts on the aquatic environment (Middlesex University et al., 2003).

By combining the two functionalities, stormwater detention ponds contribute to the overall improvement of water quality in urban environments. They act as temporary storage and treatment systems for stormwater and allow the removal of pollutants and reduction of hydraulic impacts of the discharged stormwater.

The concentration and composition of particulates and xenobiotics in stormwater depend on the materials used on the catchment surfaces and surrounding activities and can vary significantly between different catchments (Eriksson et al., 2007). The need for stormwater treatment has been recognized since the 1970s, when treatment of stormwater began in the USA. In Denmark, initial initiatives were also taken around the same time, but stormwater treatment only became commonly used after the year 2000 (Hvitved-Jacobsen et al., 2010). Wet detention ponds emerged as the most popular technology due to their simplicity and cost-efficiency. However, as particulate-bounded pollutants settle at the bottom, the hydraulic capacity of the pond will gradually decrease over time unless the sediments are regularly removed. Over time, the deposition of sediment reduces the pond's volume and, consequently, its purification efficiency. Therefore, it is important to monitor and maintain the stormwater detention ponds to ensure the functionality of their pollutant removal efficiency.

The sediment load carried by the stormwater determines the lifespan of the detention pond, and as mentioned, the load can vary significantly from one catchment to another. However, removing the sediment is a time-consuming, complex, and expensive process. The cost of renovating a pond to restore its original volume often matches or even exceeds the cost of constructing a new pond. This high cost of restoration is mainly caused by the submerged and polluted nature of the sediment, making it challenging to excavate and dispose due to its high-water content (US EPA, 2009).

2. The experimental SUDS facility at AAU

The developments and experimental work are performed using the AAU experimental SUDS facility. The experimental SUDS facility receives separated stormwater from a nearby urban catchment of about 5 ha. The facility consists of four main structures: the inlet structure, the main basin, outlet pumps and the detention basin. Figure 2.1 presents an overview of the contributing catchment and the location of the facility. In addition, figure 2.2 and 2.3 presents a schematic overview of the facility.

Figure 2.1: Overview of the catchment and the AAU experimental SUDS facility in Northern Jutland, Denmark.

2.1. The concept and structure of the facility

The fundamental concept of the SUDS facility is to separate the two essential functions of a conventional stormwater detention pond: the stormwater detention and stormwater treatment through sedimentation of particulates. The idea is to have two separated volume sections: one optimized for sedimentation and one designed for detention. This separation allows for more controlled and sophisticated treatment of everyday rainfall events, whereas more extreme and rare rainfall events can completely or partly be bypassed the treatment section and be led directly to the detention section.

By controlling the in- and outflow to the treatment section, the residence time can vary during different stages of the rainfall event, ensuring that for example, the first part of the event has a longer residence time than the last

part of the event. This facilitates a more efficient sedimentation of particulate matter from the stormwater in, for instance, the case of first flush effects.

During dry weather between rainfall events, the sediment can be drained dry. This has several benefits: Firstly, it reduces the organic fraction of the sediment by decomposition, and so may some of the hydrocarbon pollutants trapped in the sediment. Additionally, draining the sediment helps reducing the maintenance cost of regular removal of the sediment, that is needed to ensure the long-term efficiency of the stormwater treatment.

Figure 2.2: Schematic overview of the system.

Figure 2.3: Schematic sideview of the inlet structure, main basin, and pump system.

2.1.1. The inlet structure

The stormwater is collected by the residential catchment and is diverted through the separated storm drainage system to the inlet structure shown in figure 2.4. The purpose of the inlet structure is to control whether the stormwater should be diverted into the main basin or bypassed directly to the retention basin. The inlet to the main basin is controlled by a motorized sliding valve. If the sliding valve is closed, the water level raises in the inlet structure until it overflows the weir in the inlet structure and by-passes to the retention basin.

The elevation of the weir edge to the by-pass, can be manually adjusted, consequently setting the maximum water depth if the sliding valve is open, as illustrated in figure 2.3. When the maximum water depth of the main basin is

reached, the stormwater exceeding the storage capacity of the main basin will be bypassed to the retention pond. In this way, the experimental facility is designed so that everyday rainfall events will be fully treated in the main basin, whereas heavier extreme rainfall events only will be partly treated in the main basin until its capacity is reached.

In the inlet structure, two water level sensors located on each side of the weir are installed.

Figure 2.4: The inlet structure to the main basin. At the top of the image, the motorized valve towards the main basin can be seen. On the left, the manually controlled weir is visible, as well as the pipe entrance for the by-pass to the retention basin.

2.1.2. The main basin

The main basin is constructed in concrete, is 5 m long, 20 m wide, and has a total volume of 230 m³. Across the main basin are two bridges, that can be used for inspection and installation of experimental equipment. The main function of the basin is to trap organic and inorganic sediments from the stormwater, by sedimentation and settling to the bottom. In the basin, it is possible to install different insert structures (walls, baffles, porous medias etc.) to facilitate the settling process of particles and improving and optimising the stormwater treatment. Furthermore, access to the main basin by servicing trucks is ensured to ease the maintenance and clean-up of the trapped sediments.

The sedimentation basin is equipped with sensors that log the water level at both ends of the basin, meaning near the inlet and near the outlet of the main basin.

The outflow from the main basin to the retention basin is regulated by two frequency-controlled pumps. A small pump with a maximum flow of 12.5 m³/hr and a larger pump with a maximum flow of 46 m³/hr. The pumps can be operated individually and in combination, facilitating a wide range of possible regulations of the outflow from the

basin. The outflow from the basing is continuously monitored and logged by two flow gauges installed in the small building with technical installations.

Figure 2.5: The SUDS facility. Left image shows the inlet structure, main basin, and the small building with technical installations. Right image shows the main basin with the porous wall installed.

As shown in right image of figure 2.5, a porous wall is installed in the main basin. The porous wall is located 3 m from the inlet and has a thickness of 1 m and cover the full width and depth of the basin. The porous wall is constructed from fascine elements normally used for infiltration of stormwater. However, in the basin, the wall of fascine elements has the purpose of forming a porous barrier to break the jet of the inlet. This prevents the inlet jet from resuspending the bottom sediment, but also ensures a calm and uniform flow in the rest of the basin, which is beneficial for the sedimentation and steeling process.

2.1.3. The retention basin

The retention basin is situated north-east of the main basin (see figure 2.6) and receives the treated stormwater from the main basin, as well as the excesses stormwater diverted as by-pass from the inlet structure. Figure 2.6 shows the retention basin. The retention basin is designed as a dry retention basin and was constructed approximately 10 years prior to the establishment of the SUDS facility. Because the SUDS facility is built upstream the retention pond, its construction did not impact the discharge permit for releasing water from the retention basin into to the receiving stream. The discharge permit from the retention pond to the receiving stream is 15 L/s. The retention basin has a total retention volume of 725 m³, which corresponds to an estimated return period of 5 years.

The primary objective of the retention basin is to hydraulically attenuate the high peaks in stormwater runoff from the catchment in order to protect the receiving stream. As the stormwater is treated in the main basin by sedimentation and settling of organic and inorganic particulates, it is expected that the buildup of sediment within the retention basin is limited. However, the fundamental concept underlying the facility is that the majority of stormwater will be treated in the main basin, while extreme and exceptionally occurring heavy rainfall may bypass the treatment and flow directly to the retention basin. The rationale behind this is that attempting to treat the largest stormwater flows runs the risk of resuspending large fractions of the accumulated settled sediment in the main basin, resulting in flushing of sediment into the retention basin. Additionally, it is expected that extreme stormwater runoff events will only account for a small fraction of the total particulate load when compared to everyday rainfall events.

Figure 2.6: The retention basin. Top: Situation map of the retention basin. Bottom: The retention basin pictured from north-east (left) and north-west (right).

2.1.4. The receiving stream

The treated and/or delayed stormwater is discharged to the receiving stream, Landbækken, south of the project area as illustrated in figure 2.7. The stormwater is discharged to the stream through a stormwater pipe with a length of a few hundreds of meters. Landbækken is a quite small stream, that mainly receives its water from the drainage of surrounding fields and farmland. Hence, the baseflow of Landbækken is limited. Landbækken runs into the Romdrup Å, which is a larger, groundwater dependent stream transporting the water to the fjord Limfjorden.

Figure 2.7: The receiving stream, Landbækken. Left: Situation map illustrating the location of the receiving stream relative to the SUDS facility. Right: The discharge point to the stream (top) and Landbækken where it runs under the road (bottom).

2.2. Instrumentation, data access and visualization

The inlet structure of the facility is equipped with two radar water level sensors and a sliding valve with a position encoder. The main basin is equipped with two radar water level sensors: one at each end of the basin. The flow of the outlet pumps is monitored by flow gauges and the operation frequency and power consumption are monitored. Furthermore, the water level of the pump sump is measured by a radar water level sensor as well.

All the sensors' readings are collected and stored locally at the facility; therefore, data access and availability have been developed to make the data online available for the project. This has been achieved by developing a webpage, from where the current state of the facility is visualized and can be downloaded. A screen dump from the webpage is shown in Figure 2.8.

In the webpage, time series of the measurements can be seen for each of the water level sensors. By clicking on a sensor station, the time series becomes visible, and the user can then download data from the selected sensor. This also applies for the two pumps whereby historical pump flow can be accessed.

Figure 2.8: Screen dump of the webpage visualizing the current state of the experimental SUDS facility.

All the radar-based water level sensors are of the type Micropilot FMR20 from Endress+Hauser (EH, 2023). The sensor uses pulses of electromagnetic radiation in the K-band region to measure the distance from the sensor to the water table. Based on the knowledge of the sensor location relative to the bottom, the measured distance is translated to water depth. The sensor has a measurement resolution of 1 mm and a typical accuracy of ± 2 mm.

The two flow gauges used to measure the pump flow are MagFlux models from MJK (MJK, 2023). These flowmeters employ Faraday's electromagnetic induction law to accurately measure the flow rate. Typically, this type of flow meter exhibits an accuracy of less than 0.25% when the velocity exceeds 0.2 m/s. However, at lower water velocities, the accuracy significantly decreases due to the weakened electromagnetic induction from the moving water.

To ensure precise measurements and avoid inaccuracies, the flow gauges were carefully selected based on the pump capacity and pipe diameters of the pumping system. This selection process ensures that velocities below 0.2 m/s are avoided during operation.

All the sensors are read and logged locally at the facility. From here the data is pushed to an FTP server every five minutes. Subsequently, the data is processed on the servers at Aalborg University and posted to a dedicated web server, providing an interpretation of the data to visualize the current state of the facility, and offering online access for downloading.

By default, the pumps responsible for generating the outflow from the main basin are controlled locally using a logical pump controller. However, as part of the project's efforts to enhance sensor data accessibility and visualization, the local pump control logic can be modified to accept input that can be remotely sent to the facility via FTP.

3. Sediment transport and load from the catchment

The primary function of main basin at the SUDS facility is to treat and retain pollutants from the stormwater before it is released to the receiving stream. However, as the sediment particles and pollutants originate from the urban catchment surfaces and are washed off into the drainage system by the stormwater, the transport is greatly dependent on the drainage systems ability to transport the sediments and hence the pollutants.

The drainage systems ability to transport sediment is of general importance for its daily operation, as it is essential to prevent any permanent deposition of sediments within the system, since this could lead to a decrease in the water-carrying capacity and, in severe cases, blockage and clogging of the system (Winter et al. 2011). Therefore, well designed urban drainage systems are expected to have a self-cleaning sediment transport capacity.

In relation to the specific stormwater catchment contributing to the SUDS facility, its general ability to transport sediments has been investigated to identify if sediments are expected to be transported by the system to the SUDS facility and/or if first flush effects are to be expected.

3.1. Self-cleaning and sediment transport from the contributing stormwater catchment

To evaluate the transport of sediments washed off the urban surfaces into the drainage system, the shear stresses within the stormwater system are examined. It is crucial for the shear stresses of the system to exceed a critical threshold to ensure efficient self-cleaning. According to the Danish design code (Dansk Standard, 2020) a minimum shear stress of 1.5 Pa is necessary to achieve adequate self-cleaning of stormwater pipes, and that this requirement can be reduced by 10% for steel and plastic pipes. It is, however, worth noting that the shear stress threshold is not a fixed value. For instance, Winter et al. (2011) reported that as threshold of up to 3-4 Pa may be required to secure sufficient self-cleaning of stormwater pipes regardless of the construction material.

The individual stormwater pipes of the system are evaluated according to Dansk Standard (2020) for a flow corresponding to 10% of the full capacity flow. The temperature of the water is assumed to 10°C, while the roughness for plastic and concrete pipes is assumed to be 0.6 and 1.5 mm, respectively. The assumed roughness is based on an expected increase of the pipe roughness for pipes in operation compared to newly laid pipes.

The full flow capacity is estimated using the Darcy-Weisbach's formula, as formulated by Brorsen and Larsen (2009) under the assumption of stationary and uniform flow conditions, meaning that the pipe slope equals the energy gradient.

$$Q_{full} = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot g \cdot I \cdot R_{full} \cdot A_{full}^2}{f}} \quad \text{Eq. 3.1}$$

Where:

Q_{full}	Full flow capacity	$[m^3/s]$
g	Gravitational acceleration	$[m/s^2]$
I	Energy gradient	$[m/m]$
R_{full}	Hydraulic radius, full	$[m]$
A_{full}	Cross section area, full	$[m^2]$
f	Friction factor	$[-]$

The hydraulic radius for the full flowing pipe is determined as:

$$R_{full} = \frac{D}{4} \quad \text{Eq. 3.2}$$

Where:

D	Pipe diameter	$[m]$
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The friction factor f is determined iteratively by the Colebrooke and White's formula (Borsen and Larsen, 2009):

$$f = \frac{2}{\left(6.4 - 2.45 \cdot \ln\left(\frac{\kappa}{R_{full}} + \frac{4.7}{Re\sqrt{f}}\right)\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 3.3}$$

$$Re = \frac{v_{full} \cdot R_{full}}{\nu} \quad \text{Eq. 3.4}$$

Where:

κ	Equivalent grain roughness	$[m]$
Re	Reynolds number	$[-]$
v_{full}	Mean velocity, full	$[m/s]$
ν	Kinematic viscosity	$[m^2/s]$

The pipe water depth, y at 10% of full flow is determined by Bretting's formula (Borsen and Larsen, 2009):

$$\frac{Q}{Q_{full}} = 0.46 - 0.5 \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\pi \cdot y}{D}\right) + 0.04 \cdot \cos\left(\frac{2 \cdot \pi \cdot y}{D}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.5}$$

Where:

y	Water depth	$[m]$
Q	flow	$[m^3/s]$

Based on the water depth, the pipe shear stress, τ can be estimated as (Borsen and Larsen, 2009):

$$\tau = \rho \cdot g \cdot I \cdot R \quad \text{Eq. 3.6}$$

Where:

τ	Shear stress	$[N/m^2]$ or $[Pa]$
ρ	Density of water	$[kg/m^3]$
R	Hydraulic radius, 10% of full flow	$[m]$

The hydraulic radius at 10% of full flow capacity is estimated by the water dept from Eq. 3.5 by:

$$R = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\sin(\theta)}{\theta} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.7}$$

$$\theta = 2 \cdot \arccos \left(1 - \frac{2 \cdot y}{D} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.8}$$

Where:

θ | Angle from centre to the water table [m]

Figure 3.1 illustrates the self-cleaning capacity in the contributing stormwater drainage system, determined by the above procedure. As shown, there are only two pipe sections that do not meet the self-cleaning criteria of 3-4 Pa of Winter et al. (2011). However, the shear stresses comply with the requirements of 1,5 Pa in Dansk Standard (2020). Based on this, it is concluded that the contributing stormwater drainage system has an overall fairly good self-cleaning capacity.

Figure 3.1: Estimated wall shear stress of stormwater drainage system in the contributing catchment.

In addition, it is also evaluated which maximum particle sizes that are to be expected to be transported under the self-cleaning flow criteria, applying Shield's parameter (Southard, 2006). Shield estimated empirically, the maximum size of particle diameter that can be transported, conditional to the shear stress. However, the empirical foundation for method has been updated and expanded over time (Southard, 2006).

Shield's parameter is determined as:

$$\Phi = \frac{\tau}{(\rho_s - \rho) \cdot g \cdot d} \quad \text{Eq. 3.9}$$

Where:

Φ	Shield's parameter	[m]
ρ_s	Particle density	[kg/m ³]
d	Particle diameter	[m]

Whether the threshold, or the critical shear stress for the investigated particle size, is exceeded, is determined based on the relationship between the Shields' parameter, the critical Reynolds number, and the Shield's diagram in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Shields diagram. If the relationship between Shield's parameter and the critical boundary-Reynolds number is above the curve, the sediment is expected to be transported. Southard (2006).

The boundary-Reynolds number is unitless and describes the dynamics in turbulence and shear stress at the boundary. The boundary-Reynolds number is defined as (Southard, 2006):

$$Re_* = \frac{U_* \cdot d}{\nu} \quad \text{Eq. 3.10}$$

Where:

U_*	Shear velocity	[m/s]
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The shear velocity is not an actual velocity, but a quantity in which the shear stress is included, having the same unit as velocity:

$$U_* = \sqrt{\tau/\rho} \quad \text{Eq. 3.11}$$

Table 3.1 summarises the findings for the self-cleaning potential of the contributing stormwater drainage system. The temperature of the water is assumed to be 10°C, while the particle density is assumed to be 2,650 kg/m³ for the estimation of the maximum particle size to be transported.

Table 3.1: Shear stress and maximum particle sizes that can be transported at 10% of full capacity flow in the stormwater pipes of the system.

Pipe	Shear stress, τ [Pa]	Max. particle diameter [mm]	Shields Parameter, Φ [-]	boundary-Reynold number, Re_* [-]
1.1	14.4	20	0.0459	1837.25
1.2	15.3	20	0.0487	1893.79
1.3	11.9	15	0.0505	1252.63
1.4	2	2	0.0637	68.47
1.5	4	4	0.0637	193.66
1.6	3.2	3	0.0680	129.91
1.7	23.2	22	0.0672	2565.21
2.1	13.9	19	0.0466	1714.82
2.2	9.4	10	0.0599	742.20
3.1	15.9	20	0.0506	1930.57
3.2	10.9	14	0.0496	1118.92
3.3	11	15	0.0467	1204.33
3.4	11.1	15	0.0471	1209.79
3.5	10.8	15	0.0459	1193.33
4.1	2.8	2	0.0892	81.02
4.2	4.6	4	0.0733	207.68
4.3	9.3	11	0.0539	812.07

Table 3.1 presents the analysis results, demonstrating that relatively large particle sizes can be transported in most of the stormwater drainage system. This is particularly evident in the upper part of the system, where the terrain's significant slopes and corresponding pipe slopes facilitate the transport. However, further downstream in the system, the maximum particle sizes that can be transported become smaller. In relation to the evaluation of shear stresses, it was found that pipeline section 1.4 failed to meet the self-cleaning requirement over 3 Pa, according to Winter et al. (2011). Despite this, the study using the Shields parameter and Shields curve indicates that relatively large particles can be transported, even under low flow conditions.

3.2. Sediment load of total suspended solids under rainfall

Although the contributing catchment is expected to be fairly well self-cleaning, sediment might buildup on the catchment surfaces and in the system between rainfall events. The majority of sediments and harmful substances are mobilized and transported during daily rain events, while only a small part of the total amount is transported during heavy rain events.

The hypothesis is based on the fact that stormwater runoff will have a higher concentration of particles during the first period of the rain event, after which the concentration will decrease. It will therefore be most beneficial to clean the first part of the stormwater runoff if all the stormwater cannot be treated.

The content of particles in the rainwater will to some extent depend on the preceding dry weather period before the studied rain event. It has therefore been attempted to take stormwater samples both for events with short and long preceding dry weather periods.

3.2.1. Experimental setup

The stormwater samples are collected in the inlet structure of the experimental SUDS facility before it enters the main basin. The water samples are collected using an auto-sampler of the brand Teledyne ISCO 3700 Full-size portable sampler (Teledyne, 2023). The autosampler contains 24 bottles of 1 L each, and the samples were taken as discrete samples with a volume of 1 L and one sample per bottle. The intervals used vary according to the analysed rain event, but primarily between 5 and 10 min. The auto-sampler consists of a peristaltic pump that pumps the water up through the sampling tube to which a sampling nozzle is attached. Before each sampling is started, the sampling tube is blown empty to ensure that the samples are not affected by water and sediment from previous samples.

The auto-sampler was installed on the ground next to the inlet structure. The sampling nozzle was placed in the pipe of the inlet structure while the sampling tube was clamped to ensure that the sampling nozzle did not move during sampling. The experimental setup is illustrated in figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Sampling setup at the inlet structure. Left: sampling tube with nozzle. Right: The auto-sampler

3.2.2. Recorded rainfall events and inflow to the facility

A total of two rain events have been measured. The rain events vary both in time and intensity, as well as how long the preceding dry weather period has been. Table 3.2 describes the characteristics of the recorded rain events.

Table 3.2: Characteristics of the recorded rainfall events.

Event	Duration	Rain depth [mm]	Runoff volume [m ³]	Preceding dry weather period	Number of samples [n]
1	1 hr 58 min	2.0	23.7	14 days	10
2	5 hr 38 min	4.2	58.3	1 day	23

In addition, rain gauge measurements from the nearest meteorological tipping-bucket rain gauge are presented in figure 3.4. The rain gauge is located approximately 1,200 m south of the experimental SUDS facility.

Figure 3.4: Recorded rainfall events measured by the nearest meteorological tipping-bucket rain gauge approx. 1,200 m south of the facility.

Figure 3.5: Inlet flow to the facility during the recorded events and the measured rain intensity during the event.

As seen in figure 3.4 both recorded events contained relatively low-intense precipitation. Furthermore, the precipitation of the first event consisted partially of sleet. During the event, the air temperature was approx. 1 °C. Therefore, a delay was observed from the start of the event to the inflow occurred at the facility, as the sleet from roads and roofs had to melt. It was observed that there was a small accumulation of snow/sleet on the roofs of the houses in the catchment, but it melted relatively quickly.

Based on the water level measurements in the main basin and the pump sump, the inflow to the facility can be estimated for rainfall events. The water level is measured continuously at both ends of the main basin close to the inlet and outlet. During the rainfall event, the outlet pumps were kept turned off, meaning that the inflow to the facility can be estimated as the change in water volume over time in the main basin and the pump sump. Figure 3.5 shows the estimated inflow to the facility during the two events.

3.2.3. Total Suspended Solids (TSS) of the stormwater and evaluation of first flush effects

The stormwater samples were analyzed for the total content of suspended solids (TSS) in the laboratory (APHA and AWWA, 2017) in order to investigate how the TSS content varies during the event. The TSS content of the stormwater samples was determined by filtering the samples through a micro-glassfiber filter, with a grid-size of 1.2 µm and a diameter of 47 mm. The filtering was performed using vacuum forcing the water sample through the filter. The samples were filtered through individual filters and after the filtering, the filters were dried in an oven at 105°C until the dried weight had stabilized. The TSS content was determined based on the weight of the trapped particles > 1.2 µm and the filtered sample volume:

$$TSS = \frac{m_{particles}}{V_{sample}} \quad \text{Eq. 3.12}$$

Where:

TSS	Total Suspended Solid content	$[mg/L]$
$m_{particles}$	Dry weight of filtered particles	$[mg]$

V_{sample} | Filtered sample volume [L]

Figure 3.6 shows the dried filters containing the samples from event 2.

Figure 3.6: TSS samples on the filters after drying. The first sample taken is the upper left and the order of sampling goes from left to right.

Figure 3.7: TSS concentration measurements during the two recorded events

Figure 3.7 presents the result of the TSS measurements, showing the variations in TSS content during the two events. Unfortunately, it must be noted that a malfunction in the autosampler prevented the collection of water

samples during the initial 30 minutes of event 1 (top figure 3.7). For event 1 it is seen, that the TSS concentration of the water samples is relatively stable. However, it remains uncertain whether there was a peak in concentrations during the first 30 minutes of the event, as no samples were obtained during that period. Nonetheless, the highest recorded TSS content for the first event was 18 mgTSS/L, and it was found in the first water sample.

The TSS content of event 2 is considerably higher and contains more variability compared to event 1. The TSS content was found to be up to 5 times higher than in event 1. Moreover, it is also clear that the highest TSS concentrations are observed at the beginning of the event, indicating that a large fraction of the sediment load is transported in the first part of the catchment stormwater runoff, indicating the presence of first flush effects.

The definition of first flush varies in the literature. Vorreiter and Hickly (1994) define it as 40-60% of the total pollutant load being present in the first 25% of the runoff volume. On the other hand, Bertrand-Krajewski et al. (1998) provide a slightly stricter definition, stating that 80% of the total pollutant load must be found in the first 30% of the total runoff volume.

The first flush severity can be quantified based on the relative accumulated water volume and the relative accumulated mass of the pollutant during a rainfall event (Hvitved-Jacobsen et al., 2010).

$$f_{flow}(i) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i \cdot \Delta t}{\sum_{j=1}^n Q_j \cdot \Delta t} \quad \text{Eq. 3.13}$$

$$f_{mass}(i) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N c_i \cdot Q_i \cdot \Delta t}{\sum_{j=1}^J c_j \cdot Q_j \cdot \Delta t} \quad \text{Eq. 3.14}$$

Where:

$f_{flow}(i)$	Relative accumulated volume at interval i	[-]
$f_{mass}(i)$	Relative accumulated mass at interval i	[-]
$i = 1, \dots, I$	Interval number	[No.]
$j = 1, \dots, J$	Interval number	[No.]
n	Number of intervals	[No.]
Δt	Time interval	[s]
Q_i, Q_j	Flow at interval i and j respectively	[L/s]
c_i, c_j	Concentration at interval i and j respectively	[mg/L]

By plotting the relative accumulated mass as function of the relative accumulated volume, the obtained Mass-Volume curve indicate first flush effect if it is above the bisector line. The magnitude of the of the first flush effect is expressed by the deviation from the bisector. The relative accumulated Mass-Volume curves for the two events are shown in figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8: Relative accumulated Mass-Volume curve for the two events.

As figure 3.8 illustrates, the relative accumulated Mass-Volume curve varies significantly between the two investigated events. For Event 1, it can be observed that there is no measured contribution of TSS during the first 25% of the total runoff volume. This is most likely misleading, as the malfunctioning autosampler prevented the collection of water samples during the first 30 minutes of the event. Consequently, first flush effects of this event can unfortunately not be adequately assessed.

Event 2, on the other hand, shows a relative accumulated Mass-Volume curve that deviate significantly from the bisector. The Mass-Volume curve lies well above the bisector line, indicating a potential first flush. In figure 3.8, the

criteria for first flush according to Vorreiter and Hickey (1994) and Bertrand-Krajewski et al. (1998) are indicated with dotted and dash-dotted line, respectively. It can be seen that the event and the content of TSS can be characterized as a first flush based on the criterion of Vorreiter and Hickey (1994). However, the stricter definition by Bertrand-Krajewski et al. (1998) is not fulfilled. During event 2, 50% of the TSS mass is transported within first 25% of the runoff stormwater volume. This demonstrates that there exists a potential for improving the treatment of the stormwater runoff by controlling the residence time during the rainfall event facilitating the settling, even for everyday events like event 2 without a significant preceding dry weather period.

4. Characterization of the settled sediment in the main basin

The main basin has a porous wall installed that is 1 m thick and is extending across the entire width and depth of the basin. The porous wall is shown in figure 2.5 and is situated 3 m from the inlet. It is constructed from fascine elements commonly used for infiltration. The implementation of the porous wall serves two primary objectives. Firstly, it aims to disrupt the force of the inlet jet, effectively preventing the formation of violent turbulent flows within the main basin, and thus preventing resuspension of the settled sediment. Secondly, the porous wall also serves the purpose of segregating the sediment into different fractions with different particle sizes. The reasoning behind this design approach is that particle-bounded pollutants such as PAHs, metals, and heavy metals are predominantly associated with the finer sediment fractions (Bentzen, 2008; Vollertsen et al. 2012). Thus, by separating the sediment into distinct sizes, it facilitates the possibility to address and manage the specific pollutant-bound particles in the basin. To investigate this concept sediments samples have been taken from the bed sediment to be characterised and analysed for heavy metals.

4.1. Grain-size distribution and organic matter content of the sediment

The sampling is distributed as follows: a total of nine samples were taken between the inlet of the basin and the porous wall, while four samples were collected after the wall and towards the basin's outlet. From the inlet to the fascine wall, a clear variation in sediment sizes and their deposition patterns was observed. In figure 4.1 (left), it can be seen that no sediment is deposited through the middle of the basin, likely due to the turbulence created by the flow of stormwater from the inlet to the basin. The porous wall brakes and interrupts the inlet jet, causing the water to move into two swirling motions visible from the sediment deposition patterns.

Figure 4.1: Sediments deposits at the main basin. Left: before the porous wall. Right: After the wall

It is clear that sediments of different sizes are deposited in different places within these whirlpools. Fine materials are deposited right in the middle of the whirlpools (the black areas in both centres), while coarser fractions are deposited around them. Outside the coarser fractions, there is hardly any material deposition, probably due to high flow velocities. In the corners closest to the inlet, it can be observed that the majority of the deposited material is very fine. Towards the rear, near the fascine wall, there is a mixture of coarser particles (even large gravels) and finer particles that have settled. Throughout the area before the fascine wall, there was approximately 5 cm of water.

After the porous wall, it was observed that the coarsest particles had settled before or within the fascine wall area. From the fascine wall towards the outlet, there was only a thin layer of sediments, which is why four samples were collected at different distances from the fascine wall.

The location of the collected sediment samples is shown in figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Sample location for sediment samples. The first 9 samples are located before the porous wall

Sediment samples were taken during two sampling campaigns: after approximately 5 months and 10 months of operation since cleanup, respectively. During the first campaign, all 13 points were sampled, whereas only points 1, 2, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, and 13 were sampled during the second campaign.

Sieving analysis was used to determine the grain-size distribution (Nielsen and Dam, 2019a). After oven drying, the samples were firstly sieved by hand using 8 and 16 mm sieves and then sieved in vibrating sieving towers for 20 minutes containing nine sieves with the mesh sizes of 4, 2, 1, 0.5, 0.25, 0.2, 0.125, 0.075, and 0.063 mm, respectively.

The results of the grain-size distribution of the first sampling campaign (5 months) are shown in figure 4.3 and figure 4.4 visualizes and compares the grain-size distributions with the second sampling campaign (10 months). The grain-size distributions are displayed separately for samples taken before and after the porous wall.

From the results, it is evident that there is significant variation in the in grain-sizes of the samples. However, in general, the grain-size distributions demonstrate, that the sediment particles before the porous wall are much coarser than after the wall.

Before the porous wall there are some variations in the particle size distribution between the samples. In particular, samples #1, #6, and #8 contain a relatively large fraction of fine particles compared to the other samples, which is aligned with the visual observations during the sampling.

Figure 4.3: Grain-size distributions of samples from the first sampling campaign (5 months)

Figure 4.4: Comparison of grain-size distributions of samples from the two sampling campaigns

After the porous wall, the sediments are significantly smaller compared to before the wall. It is seen that all these samples contain larger fractions of fine particles smaller than 0.063 mm, for some of them up to 50%. This observation is consistent with visual observations in the basin, where the coarsest particles were observed deposited before the fascine wall, where only smaller particles pass through. Furthermore, it is also seen that as approaching the outlet, the content of particles smaller than 0.063 mm increases.

Comparing the 10 months sampling campaign with the 5 months sampling campaign, similar overall patterns are observed. However, changes have occurred over the time period, particularly in the area before the porous wall. Samples #2 and #9, which contained a significant proportion of coarse particles at the 5 months sampling, contain after 10 months 24% and 10% more fine sand, respectively. Conversely, sample #8, which initially had a considerable content of fine particles, contains after 10 months more coarse sand and closely resembles the distribution of particles in sample #9.

The last comparable sample taken in the area before the porous wall, sample #1, is located in the corner of the basin. This sample shows no significant changes in grain-size distribution, between the two sampling campaigns.

After the porous wall, it can be observed that the same pattern of distribution among the samples is not as evident after 10 months as after 5 months. At the 5 months sampling, there was an increasing content of particles smaller than 63 μm towards the outlet, but at the 10 months sampling this relationship is not apparent. However, all the samples after the porous wall still contains a significant percentage of very fine particles.

4.1.1. Organic content of the sediment

As supplement to the sieving analysis the organic content has also been measured for a subset of the samples taken at the 5-months campaign (#1, #2, #8, #9, #10, #11, #12, and #30). The organic matter content is of particular interest as the organic content typically comprises of very fine particles capable of forming aggregates and attracting environmental pollutants (Loll and Moldrup, 2000).

The organic matter content was measured by loss of ignition, burning the samples at 550°C for 48 hours (Nielsen and Dam, 2019a). Figure 4.5 summarizes the result of the analysis.

Figure 4.5: Organic matter content of the sampled sediment measured by loss of ignition after 48 hours burning at 550°C.

As figure 4.5 demonstrates, the content of organic material varies significantly among the collected samples. The analyzed samples show organic content ranging from 0.6 % to 21 %. It is observed that samples containing large fractions of coarse sand and gravel have lower organic content. Furthermore, the experiments showed that samples containing large fractions of fine particles contain a higher proportion of organic material.

After the porous wall, the content of organic material increases towards the outlet. This follows the same trend as the sieving analysis, suggesting that the fine particle sediments also contain a higher content of organic material. The only exception is sample #12, which shows a low organic content, despite a high content of fine particles. However, this is so remarkable that it is plausible that there might be an error, and conducting a duplicate determination should have been carried out to ensure accuracy.

4.2. Heavy metal concentration of the sediment

The management of the handling of the collected sediments greatly depends on the degree of contamination of the sediments. The analysis of heavy metal concentrations in the sediment aims to determine the pollution level of the sediment, and several heavy metals are considered in determining the pollution class for soil and sediments. However, analysing the sediments for heavy metals also aims to investigate how the concentration is distributed in the main basin and to evaluate if the porous wall is likely to have an effect on where the heavy metals pollution is concentrated.

A total of seven sediment samples were collected in the main basin. The samples were taken after approximately 7 months of operation since the cleanup, in between the 5 months and 10 months sampling campaigns for particle size distribution analysis. Four of the collected seven samples were taken before the porous wall, and three samples were taken after the wall. The sample locations are shown in figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6: Sampling locations for the heavy metal analysis

The samples for the heavy metal analysis are labelled T1, T2, etc. However, the four samples before the porous wall were taken in the same locations as samples #1, #2, #8, and #9 used for particle size distribution analysis. Downstream the porous wall, a sample was taken immediately after the wall (T5), and another sample was collected in the downstream-left corner of the main basin (T6), as well as in the depression around the outlet (T7).

The sediment was collected as loose grab samples and brought to the laboratory for analyses. To avoid contamination of the samples with metals, which could later be traced in the heavy metal analyses, the small shovel used for sampling was wrapped in plastic.

The heavy metal analyses are performed using the ICP-OES (Inductively Coupled Plasma - Optical Emission Spectroscopy) method. The analyses are conducted on a Thermo Fisher Scientific iCAP 6300 ICP-OES instrument equipped with an autosampler.

The ICP instrument is calibrated to measure specific wavelengths for cadmium, copper, chromium, nickel, lead, and zinc. Additionally, it is calibrated to measure the content of phosphorus in the samples. The results are expressed in parts per billion (ppb) for cadmium, copper, chromium, nickel, and phosphorus. For nickel and lead, three and two wavelengths, respectively, are selected for measurements as shown in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Wavelengths applied for the ICP-analysis.

Element	Wavelength [nm]
Copper (Cu)	224.7, 324.7, 327.3
Chrom (Cr)	267.7, 283.5, 284.3
Cadmium (Cd)	214.4, 226.5, 228.8
Nickel (Ni)	221.6, 231.6, 341.4
Zinc (Zn)	202.5, 206.2
Lead (Pb)	220.3
Phosphorus (P)	177.4, 178.2, 213.6

The results of the heavy metal analyses of the samples are shown in table 4.2. The concentrations are given as the average of double and triple determinations.

Table 4.2: Wavelengths applied for the ICP-analysis.

Sample	Cd mg/kg TS	Cr mg/kg TS	Cu mg/kg TS	Ni mg/kg TS	Pb mg/kg TS	Zn mg/kg TS	P mg/kg TS
T1	0.15	4.3	13.4	4.6	4.9	300.4	311.7
T2	0.08	1.6	3.3	2.2	1.8	71.5	199.0
T3	0.14	5.1	11.4	3.8	3.6	247.3	324.6
T4	0.07	2.3	5.7	2.2	3.6	90.9	413.14
T5	0.27	7.4	22.2	5.9	8.4	516.4	533.6
T6	0.55	15.4	47.3	9.8	15.4	1254.7	1288.3
T7	0.24	7.7	16.3	6.0	7.4	374.7	491.0

For comparison overview, the measured concentrations are visualised in figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7: Comparison of heavy metal concentrations in the main basin

Figure 4.7 compares the results of the heavy metal analyses, wherein the concentrations for the inlet samples before the porous wall are represented as average values. The figure indicates a consistent rise in heavy metal concentrations from the inlet section to the outlet section of the main basin.

The observed concentrations of zinc and copper after the porous wall are found to be twice as high as the highest concentrations detected at the front of the wall (sample T1). Specifically, the concentration of copper is measured at 25.7 mg Cu/kg TS, while the concentrations of zinc are measured at 598 mg Zn/kg TS. Similarly, the concentrations of other heavy metals (namely, lead, chromium, cadmium, and nickel) are also elevated on the rear side of the porous wall. The degree of concentration difference varies between 1.5 to 2.0 times when compared to the highest concentrations detected at the front of the fascine wall.

The highest recorded concentrations are concentrated within the corner of the basin adjacent to the outlet (T6). As for sample T7, the heavy metal concentrations remain notably elevated in comparison to those before the porous wall although they are not as elevated as those in T5 and T6.

The samples for analysing the concentrations of heavy metals are, as previously described, collected from the same locations in the sedimentation basin as parts of the samples for analysing particle size distributions. When the concentrations are compared with the particle size distributions - where possible - it is observed that the concentrations of heavy metals are high in areas where significant amounts of fine sediment (>63 µm) were found. This corresponds to the fact that pollution is more likely to be bound to fine sediment.

The results also demonstrate that it is possible to segregate the sediment into fractions with significant differences in the amount of pollution: the sediment before the porous wall is slightly polluted, while the sediments further inside the basin are moderately to heavily polluted according to (MFVM, 2015). This clearly demonstrates the potential for improving the hydrodynamic design of stormwater detention ponds.

5. CFD modelling of the main basin

CFD modelling (Computational Fluid Dynamics) of the basin has been used to evaluate different configuration strategies for the hydrodynamic design of the main basin.

5.1. Evaluation of the inlet section of the main basin

The inlet sets the standard for the entire basin's further function. It is therefore important that as good conditions for sedimentation as possible are created early on.

The inlet section must break the inlet jet and create a stable flow through the rest of the basin. The analysed inlet configurations must - in addition to spreading the flow - create turbulence around the inlet. With this, energy is taken out of the flow, and the flow velocities are thus reduced. The stable flow through the basin will then take place in the majority of the basin's cross-section. If the inlet is not considered thoroughly, short circuits and dead zones may occur in the basin. The minimization of these zones will result in longer effective residence time in the basin. The overall goal of the configurations is therefore to create a uniform and well-distributed residence of water flowing through the basin.

A total of three inlet configurations are evaluated and compared to a reference without any inlet configuration.

1. Porous wall
2. Manifold
3. Baffle and diverted inlet jet

Figure 5.1: Inlet configurations. (a) Porous wall. (b) Manifold. (c) Baffle and diverted inlet jet

The Porous wall inlet configuration is intended to spread the inlet jet so that the flow velocity is uniform throughout the cross-section of the basin. This happens by an energy loss occurring across the porous wall. The energy loss will cause the flow velocities to drop on the back side of the porous wall. On the front of the porous wall, large turbulence will occur, which will cause dissipation of energy from the inlet jet. The porous wall with a thickness of 1 m is placed 3 m from the inlet jet. The modelling of the transition between the free basin volume and the porous wall will require very small calculation cells. Thus, the configuration is simplified so that the tube is modelled as a porous medium in Star-CCM+. The configuration can be seen in figure 5.1 (a).

The Manifold inlet configuration is also based on the idea of spreading the flow over the entire width of the basin. The manifold is attached to the inlet pipe, and the water is led out through the manifold's eight downward-facing nozzles. In this way, good conditions are created for utilising of the cross-section, even before the water reaches the basin. In addition, the speed of the inlet jet is reduced since the water must be distributed in the manifold's

eight nozzles. The manifold is modelled with the same diameter as the inlet pipe, 0.5 m in diameter, while the eight downward-facing nozzles has a selected diameter of 0.18 m each, which combined have the same total cross-sectional area as the inlet pipe. The configuration can be seen in figure 5.1 (b).

The last evaluated inlet configuration: Baffle and diverted inlet jet is, as the name indicates, a combination of diverting the inlet jet at a 90-degree angle and a baffle plate. The intention is to create a longer flow path for the water and optimize the dissipation of the energy from the inlet jet. The inlet is diverted towards the side of the basin where the flow is restricted by the baffle. The baffle inserted 2.5 m from the inlet is open on the side opposite to the diverted jet and covers 75% of the width of the basin. The location of the baffle is determined based on Thackston et al. (1987), who state that a well-placed baffle with a length of 75% of the basin width may increase the length-width ratio by a factor of 3-4. The turbulence in the area between the diverted inlet and the baffle is intended to reduce the flow velocity, while the water must be forced back around the baffle which lengthens the flow path. The configuration can be seen in figure 5.1 (c).

5.1.1. Model setup

Simulations of the flows in the main basin with the three different inlet configurations have been carried out under stationary conditions using Star-CCM+ CFD software (Siemens, 2020). It has been chosen to model the basin in a one-phase model, where the basin is completely filled with water. The modelling is carried out on the assumption that the water is incompressible, and thus with constant density. In Star-CCM+, the Segregated Flow solver works optimally for handling incompressible fluids and is therefore used in the flow model.

Regarding the three-dimensional modelling of the flow in the main basin, the time-averaged Navier-Stokes equations are applied. As the flow is expected to be highly turbulent in a large fraction of the main basin, the application of turbulence model is needed since turbulence affects mass transport and momentum in the flow. However, the choice of turbulence model can have an impact on the results. Hence, a comparison has been made between the turbulence models Realizable $k-\epsilon$ Two-Layer and $k-\omega$ SST (Menter). The models have been evaluated based on the simulated flow of the main basin without any inlet configurations. Based on this evaluation, it is found that for the Realizable $k-\epsilon$ Two-Layer model, symmetry occurs around the centre through the basin, whereas symmetry is not simulated with the $k-\omega$ SST (Menter) model. In connection with simulation, Liu (2017) has found that the flows through a rectangular basin are asymmetric, with the asymmetry increasing at higher flow rates, which is supported by Stovin and Saul (1996). This agrees with the simulations for the $k-\omega$ SST (Menter) model. Yan et al. (2014) also state in a comparison between the two turbulence models that results with the $k-\omega$ SST (Menter) model result is in the best agreement with experimental measurements. The $k-\omega$ SST (Menter) model is therefore chosen for further modelling.

In CFD modelling, the flow volume is subdivided into a computational mesh to solve the time-averaged averaged Navier-Stokes equations. Ideally, the choice of computational mesh should be independent of the modelled result. However, this is not the case if the mesh is too coarse. On the other hand, an unnecessary fine mesh requires large computational power; thus, selecting the calculation mesh in CFD modelling is often a trade-off between model accuracy and simulation time. Thus, a mesh analysis has been performed to identify a descent and applicable mesh size for the simulations. The analysis was performed by simulating the flow of the main basin without any inlet configurations starting with a coarse mesh, which was gradually refined until the model result converged. This resulted in a calculation mesh with a total of approximately 1 million mesh cells with specific refinements for the inlet pipe, outlet pipe and the inlet section of the basin. Cubic calculation cells were selected, as cubic mesh cells

typically are beneficial for simple geometries as well as in situations where the flow mainly follows the geometry. The mesh configuration applied for the simulations is listed in table 5.1.

Table 4.1: Summary of the mesh configuration

Base size	10 cm
Max size	150% of base size
Prism layer thickness	40% of base size
Number of prism layers	10
Refinement of the inlet section	
Max size	50% of base size
Inlet pipe	
Max size	40% of base size
Prism layer thickness	10% of base size
Number of prism layers	5
Outlet pipe	
Max size	25% of base size
Prism layer thickness	10% of base size
Number of prism layers	5

The inlet configurations are evaluated with an inflow to the facility of 34 L/s. This flow was selected based on modelling the catchment runoff using historical rainfall records from a 22-year period. Here, it has been found that 34 L/s corresponds to the 97% percentile of runoff flow from the catchment, assuming that the total runoff volume during rain events is directed to the facility with constant flow rate during the event. The boundary condition on the inlet is defined as a fully developed velocity profile corresponding to this flow.

The outlet is modelled as a pressure boundary condition. The top of the basin is defined as a plane of symmetry with no friction, neglecting the friction between the water surface and the air. For the remaining surfaces of the basin and pipes, the boundaries are defined as walls with a no-slip condition.

To evaluate the flow pattern of the different inlet configurations, neutrally buoyant ‘water’ particles are included in the modelling and injected with the inlet water. The particle tracks of the particles are modelled as a Lagrangian Multiphase in Star-CCM+, and the particles are injected into the basin when the flow patterns in the model have converged to quasi-stationary conditions.

5.1.2. Evaluating the hydrodynamic flow patterns of the inlet configurations

The flows for the reference situation (basin without any inlet configuration) reveal that the inlet jet creates a narrow advective flow directed directly towards the outlet as seen in figure 5.2. This means that the water that enters the basin moves relatively quickly towards the outlet. A short circuit is thus created, and the volume of the basin is therefore not utilized to its full potential. At about 8 m from the inlet, the jet hits the bottom of the basin. This spreads the jet, creating a wider and slower advective zone from here along the bottom towards the outlet.

Figure 5.2: Velocity patterns of the reference without any inlet configuration. *Top: horizontal plane of the basin 0.9 m above the bottom of the basin. Bottom: vertical plane through the centre line of the basin.*

Figure 5.3 shows the particle trajectories for the reference basin. Here, it can be seen that the ‘water’ particles follow the advective zone and begin to spread out at 8 m from the inlet, where the jet hits the bottom. This creates some eddies which create a mixing of the water. Some of these particles circulate back to the advective zone, while others run along the wall back towards the inlet, where the water is almost stagnant. Most of the water in the reference situation therefore flows in a more or less straight line from inlet to outlet. This means that the cross-section of the basin is not optimally used for the sedimentation processes.

Figure 5.3: Particle trajectories seen from above for the reference without any inlet configuration.

Figure 5.4 shows the velocity patterns of the porous wall inlet configuration. It is seen that the inlet jet is dispersed effectively when it hits the porous wall. Due to the resistance of the porous barrier, a return flow is created along the sides of the basin. On the rear side, the porous wall creates a uniform flow with low velocities throughout the cross-section. According to the visualised vectors, the flow is directed almost straight towards the outlet.

Figure 5.4: Velocity patterns of the porous wall configuration. *Top: horizontal plane of the basin 0.9 m above the bottom of the basin. Bottom: vertical plane through the centre line of the basin.*

The particle trajectories for the porous wall configuration are shown in figure 5.5. The trajectories show a clear and significant recirculation and mixing before the porous wall as a result of the inlet jet spreading to the sides and forming large eddies. On the rear side of the porous wall, a long, wide advective zone is seen, which covers the entire cross-section of the basin towards the outlet. It is also seen that small dead zones are formed in the corners next to the outlet. This corresponds well to the findings of heavy metals that were found to have the highest concentrations in this area of the basin. All in all, the simulations show that the porous wall configuration works as intended, dispersing the inlet jet throughout the basin's cross-section, beneficial for the sedimentation processes in the rest of the basin.

Figure 5.5: Particle trajectories seen from above for the porous wall configuration.

The manifold configuration is, similar to the porous wall configurations, also based on the idea of dispersing the inlet jet. The manifold configuration directs the water down towards the bottom of the basin via its eight nozzles as shown in figure 5.6 (top). This results in the water being dispersed over the entire width of the basin, but with larger velocities at the bottom than at the top as shown in figure 5.5 (middle) and figure 5.5 (bottom).

Figure 5.6: Velocity patterns of the Manifold configuration. Top: vertical plane through the centre of the inlet manifold. Middle: horizontal plane of the basin 0.9 m above the bottom of the basin. Bottom: vertical plane through the centre line of the basin.

The manifold configuration creates a quite chaotic flow pattern in the centre of the basin with several eddies as shown in figure 5.7. The advective zones for this configuration are primarily found along the sides of the basin as indicated by particle trajectories.

Figure 5.7: Particle trajectories seen from above for the Manifold configuration.

Compared to the other inlet configurations, the baffle configuration creates a longer flow path for the water through the basin. In figure 6.14, it can be seen that the water flows into the right side of the basin and then from here returns to the left and around the baffle. As consequence, the baffle creates higher flow velocities along the left wall of the basin, where an advective zone towards the outlet is formed.

Figure 5.8: Velocity patterns of the Baffle and diverted inlet jet configuration. Top: horizontal plane of the basin 0.9 m above the bottom of the basin. Bottom: vertical plane through the centre line of the basin.

The higher velocity in the advective zone along the top wall of the basin creates a large recirculating pattern in the centre of the basin, which can be seen in the particle trajectories in figure 5.9. Here, there are low flow velocities back towards the baffle, and the water only picks up speed towards the outlet when it comes back to the advective zone. This configuration clearly extends the flow paths of the basin, but it also seems to generate fairly large dead zones achieving this.

Figure 5.9: Particle trajectories seen from above for the Manifold configuration.

5.1.3. Evaluating the inlet configurations' influence on the residence time of the main basin

Good conditions for the sedimentation of particles in the basin depend on the residence time of the particles. The particles partly follow the flow motion of the water; therefore, the hydraulic residence time is also evaluated, as the flow patterns generated by the inlet configurations create different residence times for the water in the basin. The hydraulic residence times are investigated by introducing a conservative tracer to the models. This is modelled in Star-CCM+ as a Passive Scalar, with which it is possible to determine the effective residence time for the individual inlet configurations. This tracer is fed into the entire cross-section of the inlet pipe with a concentration of 1, after which the concentration of the passive scalar is monitored in the outlet for 6 hours of physical simulation time. In

this way, it is investigated how long it takes the water to flow from the inlet to the outlet dependent on the inlet configuration.

The residence times are analysed and compared on the basis of response curves for the concentration in the outlet, the first contact of the tracer with the outlet (t_F), the short-circuiting (S), the effective volume ratio (e), and the hydraulic efficiency (λ) for each of the four different simulations.

The parameters S , e , and λ are calculated based on the method given by Persson et al. (1999), given in equations 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4.

$$t_n = \frac{V}{Q} \quad \text{Eq. 5.1}$$

$$S = \frac{t_{16}}{t_{50}} \quad \text{Eq. 5.2}$$

$$e = \frac{t_{50}}{t_n} \quad \text{Eq. 5.3}$$

$$\lambda = \frac{t_p}{t_n} \quad \text{Eq. 5.4}$$

Where:

V	Volume of the basin	$[m^3]$
Q	Flow	$[m^3/s]$
S	Short-circuiting	$[-]$
e	Effective volume ratio	$[-]$
λ	Hydraulic efficiency	$[-]$
t_{16}	16 th percentile of the residence time distribution	$[s]$
t_{50}	Effective residence time, 50 th percentile of the residence time distribution	$[s]$
t_n	Theoretical residence time	$[s]$
t_p	Time of peak outflow concentration	$[s]$

First contact (t_F) indicates the time when the concentration of the tracer is first observed in the outlet. The time is normalized in relation to theoretical residence time. The short-circuiting (S) indicates whether the tracer is flushed out at once or whether it is flushed out over a longer period of time. The effective volume ratio (e) tells how close the effective residence time is to the theoretical residence time, and therefore also how well the basin volume is utilized. The hydraulic efficiency (λ) describes how close the time of the highest measured concentration is to the theoretical residence time. For a plug-flow, all four parameters t_F , S , e , and λ equals 1.

The theoretical residence time for the basin with an in- and outflow of 34 L/s is 1 hour and 52 minutes. The result of the simulations can be seen in figure 5.10 and figure 5.11, where the response curves for the inlet configurations and the residence time parameters are shown. On the x-axis, the time is normalized with the theoretical residence time, while the concentrations in the outlet are normalized in relation to the initial concentration on the y-axis.

Figure 5.10: Response curves of the evaluated inlet configurations. * Indicate the effective residence time, t_{50}

Figure 5.11: Residence time performance for the evaluated inlet configurations.

The reference situation without any inlet configuration has a high and narrow peak, as well as an early first contact followed by a long tail of low concentrations. This suggests that the basin mainly consists of dead zones and a small advective zone, which is seen by the relatively high degree of short-circuiting and the low effective volume ratio. This is also supported by the simulated flow patterns in figure 5.3.

For the porous wall configuration, the response curve is lower and wider with a much later first contact. The tracer is observed 10.4 times later in the outlet for the porous wall configuration compared to the reference. The slightly wider curve indicates that the flow is dominated by a large number of advective and mixing zones and only a few dead zones. This configuration has the highest degree of short-circuiting, meaning that a large part of the tracer ends up in the outlet over a short period of time. Also, it has a high hydraulic efficiency. The effective residence time is 6.7 times longer for this configuration than for the reference.

The manifold configuration has the flattest curve of the four simulations, indicating a large amount of mixing in the basin. An earlier first contact with the outlet is seen compared to the porous wall configuration, which is due to the advective zones along the basin side walls. The tracer is recorded for the first time in the outlet 4.2 times later than the reference situation. The configuration makes good use of the basin volume according to the effective volume ratio, similar to the porous wall configuration. The effective residence time of the tracer is 6.8 times longer for this configuration compared to the reference.

The flow paths created by the baffle with diverted inlet configuration have some degree of similarity with the reference. However, the peak concentration occurs later and is lower, which is due to the wider advective zone compared to the reference. The effective residence time is also significantly longer due to greater mixing, which is also the reason for the higher effective volume ratio and the lower degree of short-circuiting. The tracer is registered for the first time in the outlet 2.2 times later than for the reference. The effective residence time is 4.7 times longer in the basin for the baffle with diverted inlet configuration, compared to the reference situation.

It can therefore be seen that the design of the inlet has a great influence on the residence time in the basin. All the evaluated inlet configurations can improve the effective residence time of the basin and thus give the particles more time to settle. Of the evaluated inlet configurations, analysing the residence time indicates that the porous wall and the manifold have the best positive influence on the basin.

5.1.4. Bottom shear stress during basin filling

The purpose of the inlet configurations is, as mentioned, to ensure that the inlet jet is dispersed as best as possible over the basin's cross-section. This ensures the greatest possible dissipation of the energy from the inlet jet, facilitating an optimal use of the basin volume. In addition to this aspect, it should also be considered to what extent the configurations give rise to high bottom shear stresses when filling the sedimentation basin. High shear stresses should be avoided to reduce the resuspension of deposited particles from the bottom.

In relation to dispersion of the inlet jet and optimization of the basin volume, it can - based on residence times - be seen that the inlet configurations with porous wall and manifold perform best. Shear stresses when filling the sedimentation basin are therefore further investigated for these two inlet configurations.

Filling of the sedimentation basin is investigated in a transient two-phase model. To model both water and air, the Volume of Fluid (VOF) model is applied. An inlet flow of 80 L/s is used for the comparison. This inflow corresponds to a stormwater runoff that is expected to occur once a year from the catchment.

VOF models are usually relatively sensitive and require low time steps in the simulation. To minimize the computational time, symmetry is assumed around the longitudinal centre direction of the main basin, and therefore only one half of the basin is simulated. Thus, the result is achieved by mirroring around the symmetry plane. In addition, only the first 7.5 m of the sedimentation basin is modelled in the longitudinal direction.

Figure 5.12: Simulated bottom shear stresses during filling to 0.7 m depth.

Figure 5.12 shows the bottom shear stresses for the two inlet configurations with an inflow of 80 L/s. The bottom shear stresses are shown for different water levels. It can be seen that the shear stresses generally decrease with increasing water levels. Both models are simulated until a water level of 0.7 m is reached.

Determining an absolute shear stress threshold for resuspension of the bed sediment is associated with significant uncertainties, as it depends on the sedimentation composition and for how long the sediment has consolidated. However, Bentzen (2008) reports a critical bottom shear stress for resuspension of 0.1 Pa for stormwater pond sediment that has consolidated for 24 hours. If this threshold is assumed valid for resuspension of the sediment in the facility, it is seen that both inlet configurations are subject to resuspension at low water levels (0.1 m). However, as the water level increases, the shear stresses decrease for both configurations.

It is, however, also clear from the simulations that the configuration with porous wall reduces the area with high shear stress more effectively than the manifold configuration. In front of the porous wall, the shear stresses remain high, whereas the bottom shear stresses after the porous wall are effectively reduced.

5.2. Evaluation of the outlet section of main basin

The outlet section of the basin is the last part of the basin that the stormwater passes before it runs into the pump sump, from where it is pumped to the retention basin and from here discharged to the receiving stream. The outlet configurations must, therefore, ensure that the bottom shear stresses are minimized as much as possible, to ensure that sedimented particles are not resuspended, but retained in the basin when the main basin is emptied.

Two configurations at the outlet are investigated with a focus on reducing bottom shear stresses when emptying the basin. The investigated configurations are compared with a reference without configurations, meaning that the basin is emptied with the largest of the two outlet pumps, pumping at its full capacity of 12,8 L/s. This corresponds to how the facility is currently operated.

One active-controlled and one passive-controlled configuration is evaluated:

1. Water level-based pump control
2. Perforated outlet pipe

As the experimental SUDS facility has the possibility of adjusting the outflow of the pumps, a configuration is chosen where the pumps are controlled based on the water level in the main basin. High flow rates at low water levels are expected to cause high bottom shear stresses near the outlet. Therefore, it is chosen to initially empty with the maximum capacity of the largest pump (12.8 L/s) until a water level of 10 cm is reached. Then, the outflow is changed to the capacity corresponding to the smallest pump (3.5 L/s) until a water level of 5 cm is reached. And finally, the last 5 cm is drained at a reduced flow rate of the small pump of 1 L/s.

Perforated pipes are typically made with narrow slots or circular holes with a small diameter. This creates a smaller area for flow, which reduces the flow of water to the outlet pipe. The perforated pipe is modelled as a 0.9 m high vertical pipe on top of the outlet pipe mounted in an extension of the outlet pipe. The top surface of the perforated pipe is intended to be completely open with the same diameter as the outlet pipe. This means that water levels above 0.9 m can be drained more quickly with less risk of affecting the bottom. The modelling of the transition between the free basin volume and the perforations in the pipe will require very small calculation cells depending on the chosen size of slots or holes in the pipe. Thus, the configuration is simplified so that the perforated pipe is modelled as a porous baffle in Star-CCM+. The outlet configuration is illustrated in figure 5.13.

Figure 5.13: Perforated outlet pipe configuration.

The outlet configurations are examined in relation to the reduction of bottom shear stresses during emptying. The configurations are therefore investigated in three-dimensional VOF models in order to simulate the water level change in the basin. To reduce the computational time, it has been chosen to model only the last 5 m of the main basin, as this is the area of interest in evaluating the bottom shear stresses. Furthermore, the emptying of the basin is simulated with an initial water depth of 20 cm.

5.2.1. Bottom shear stress during emptying the basin

The bottom shear stresses for the reference outlet are shown in figure 5.14 together with a photo taken at the SUDS facility showing the distribution of the sediment in the outlet section.

Figure 5.14: Right: Simulated bottom shear stresses for the reference outlet at 2 cm water level. Left: Photo of the sediment at the facility.

The simulation shows that a large area around the outlet with shear stresses larger than 0.1 Pa. Compared to the photo taken at the facility in this area, the simulation result corresponds well to the area, where the bottom is clean for sediment. This indicates that securing the bottom shear stresses at the outlet section to be less than 0.1 Pa might significantly reduce the risk of resuspension of deposited particles.

Of the two evaluated outlet configurations, it is the configuration with the perforated pipe that works best in terms of reducing the bottom shear stresses. Figure 5.15 (right) shows that the bottom shear stresses do not exceed 0.1 Pa. Compared to the reference outlet, it is therefore not expected that there will be a significant resuspension of deposited particles caused by emptying. However, the emptying time for the configuration with the perforated pipe is long since the resistance through the pipe limits the water flow.

Figure 5.15 (left) shows no clear pattern in the shear stresses. In some places, these exceed 0.1 Pa, although to a much lesser extent than the reference outlet. The highly unstructured bottom shear stresses can be explained by some small waves that are formed by the sudden change in the outflow as part of the control strategy.

Figure 5.15: Simulated bottom shear stresses for the water level-based pump controlled outlet (left) and the Perforated outlet pipe outlet (Right), both at a water level of 2 cm.

Based on the two investigated configurations, compared to the reference outlet, it is clearly possible to reduce the bottom shear stresses during emptying. There will therefore be less risk of resuspension for both evaluated configurations if this is evaluated based a critical bottom shear stress of 0.1 Pa for resuspension. The perforated pipe limits the shear stresses the most, but also prolong the emptying time considerably. When implementing the configurations, it must therefore be considered whether the emptying time or the shear stresses are more important.

6. LSPIV installation and test at the Experimental SUDS facility

The installation of Large Scale Particle Image Velocimetry (LSPIV) equipment in the Aalborg retention pond is a milestone within the Joint Research Activities of the Co-UDlabs project. This activity was carried out from 24/10/2022 to 28/10/2022 during the visit of Juan Naves (University of A Coruña - UDC) to Aalborg University (AAU) Co-UDlabs team. The visit was carried out in the scope of the Networking Activity WP2 (Capacity building), which fosters the scientific collaboration between Co-UDlabs Partners.

Large Scale Particle Image Velocimetry is a visualization technique that UDC has been applying in its STREET and BLOCK facilities during the last 5 years to estimate surface velocities. Details of this technique can be consulted in the last related publications Naves et al. (2021, 2020).

The collaboration between UDC and AAU teams in this activity started with a first meeting during the general assembly held in A Coruña (1st July 2022). This meeting served to explore the collaboration and to agree on the convenience of the visit of Juan Naves to Aalborg to collaborate in the installation and setting up of cameras in the retention pond to estimate velocities, which may serve as calibration data for numerical models that are being developed at Aalborg University. Some preliminary videos taken using mobile phones by the AAU team were processed by the UDC team, and the feasibility and possibilities of LSPIV were discussed in a second preparation meeting on 14 September, 2022. UDC was committed to preparing and providing the needed hardware and software based on Raspberry Pi as a low-cost solution, while AAU committed to planning the installation of the cameras in the facility and the initial experiments to be performed.

6.1. Installation of LSPIV

The first step of the activity was protecting the equipment from rain and other elements. The required equipment to use the LSPIV technique in the retention pond consisted of 3 NOIR Picameras V2.1 controlled by Raspberries Pi 4. The raspberries record, store, and transmit the videos to be processed via Wi-Fi. To do this, hermetic protective boxes were adapted with 3D-printed pieces to mount the cameras and keep the Raspberries Pi inside. A metal cover has also been added to prevent rainwater on the lens of the cameras.

Figure 6.1: Encapsulating the equipment protecting it from the elements.

The raspberries have been installed on the lateral of the main basin of the facility: one recording the inlet section and the others capturing the outlet section of the tank. The raspberries and the cameras were installed inside the boxes assembled. Power supply has been provided through outdoor electrical boxes.

Figure 6.2: Installation of the equipment at the Experimental SUDS facility.

To rectify the perspective of the frames recorded by the cameras, it has been necessary to measure the dimensions of the tank and obtain the coordinates of reference elements.

Figure 6.3: Identifying and obtaining coordinate reference elements.

6.2. Inlet test

The first experiment performed was focusing on the inlet section of the retention tank. The first camera was used, and a video of 5 minutes was recorded while 800 L of water – previously storage before the inlet gate of the facility – were introduced to the facility. Sawdust was used as tracer particles and distributed on the water surface before the experiment started.

Figure 6.4: Recording the inlet.

6.3. Outlet test

Cameras 2 and 3 were used to record the movement of the particles used in the emptying of the retention tank at the outlet section. The pumps of the facility were used and videos of 1 minute were recorded during the time of emptying. When the water depth of the tank decreased, two additional videos of 5 minutes were recorded to better register the last part of the process in order to analyze how velocities increased and sediment deposited may be resuspended.

Figure 6.5: Cameras recording the outlet test and frames at the end of the experiment.

6.4. LSPIV processing

The videos recorded were first rectified using four points with known coordinates placed at the corners of the frame and measured during the installation of the cameras. A median filter of the image is then applied to highlight particles in order to be better recognized by the OpenPIV software, which is applied to the rectified and filtered images. Raw velocity results obtained were filtered to remove erroneous vectors using the noise ratio from cross-correlation function, median spatial filter, minmax filter, and median temporal filter for mean results from several results of pair of frames. Finally, the velocities are scaled to the result.

Figure 6.6: Example of frame rectification, frame filtering, raw velocity data obtained, and final filtered velocity results for the inlet test.

6.5. Results

Some of the velocity results for the inlet test are shown in figure 6.7. Each result is obtained as a mean of 10 pairs of frames recorded at 20 frames per second. As seen in the inlet results, the methodology allows obtaining the surface velocities generated in the inlet chamber as the water jet enters the tank, generating symmetrical vortices on either side of the jet. The data obtained is useful in terms of CFD calibration and understanding of processes developed in the inlet chamber of the retention tank. The absence of velocities in the area close to the position of the camera is due the framing of the camera that is not recording the first meter of water surface as seen in figure 6.4.

Figure 6.7: Example of frame rectification, frame filtering, raw velocity data obtained, and final filtered velocity results for the inlet test.

The results obtained in the emptying test carried out in the outlet chamber of the holding tank are shown in figure 6.8. In this case, the videos from cameras 2 and 3 have been joined using the area viewed by the two cameras to obtain the velocities over the entire surface of the tank. Since the emptying of the tank is slow, 8 different videos have been recorded considering the initial time when the pump was turned on. The first 6 videos - with one minute of duration and times between 0 and 41 minutes from the starting of the pumping plus an additional video recorded before the pumping - showed no affection of the pumping to surface velocities. This is due to the high depths in the tank and the pumping flow extracted through the tank sink placed at the bottom of the tank. The velocities

obtained for all these videos are similar because of the wind. The mean velocities obtained for the videos recorded at 27 mins from the start of the pump are included in figure 6.8. The influence of the pumping started at 46 minutes from the starting of the pump when the seventh video was recorded. The velocities are also included in the figure as the mean result of the video with a duration of one minute. As can be observed, surface velocities were increased towards the sink of the facility placed in the left-central part of the plot. Some vortices can be also observed in the vicinities of the traffic cone used for calibration. A last video of 5 minutes duration was recorded 51 minutes after the start of the pump, where surface velocities are increasing until the water depth goes down the sink level when no particles are moving. Although the number of valid velocity vectors from the last frames was affected by the deposition of particles when depths are extremely low, the increasing of velocities is clearly seen in the plots obtained from this video and included in figure 6.8.

Figure 6.8: Example of frame rectification, frame filtering, raw velocity data obtained and final filtered velocity results for the inlet test.

6.6. Summary

The results of the first tests are promising and the results obtained will be used for calibration and validation of the CFD models. This way, surface velocities can help to better understand the deposition and erosion processes occurring in the retention basin during filling or emptying to optimize control strategies. Further experiments with the cameras installed are being planned, and the collaboration between AAU and UDC will continue within the scope of Co-UDlabs on this research line.

7. Improve the management of detention ponds

Traditionally, rainwater detention ponds play a crucial role in mitigating the hydraulic impact on receiving waters. Research conducted in a pilot-scale detention pond at AAU in Denmark has yielded valuable insights into the separation of xenobiotic compounds within such ponds:

- a. The formation of sediments in a small urban catchment is separated within wet detention ponds.
- b. Xenobiotic compounds exhibit differential adsorption to particles of varying sizes, suggesting improved detention pond performance in removing accumulated sediments.
- c. The efficient removal of particle-bound pollutants, like heavy metals, in detention pond design depends on understanding their transport patterns. Varying particle sizes lead to different concentrations across the pond, enabling strategic pond design and operation.
- d. Retrofitting existing wet detention ponds with porous walls can enhance the separation efficiency of xenobiotic-coated particles.
- e. The combination of Large-Scale Particle Image Velocimetry (LSPIV) and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) proves to be a potent tool for comprehending and enhancing detention pond design.
- f. The dynamics of pond filling and emptying are highly variable due to changing hydrodynamics during these phases.

Considering the EC water framework directive, the management of detention ponds has gained increased significance. This research demonstrates that optimizing the design and operation of detention ponds can effectively reduce the release of xenobiotics into the environment. These insights are applicable to both existing ponds and the planning of new ponds.

8. Conclusions and contribution towards the objectives of Co-UDlabs

In conclusion, there is significant potential to enhance particle separation and boost the removal of xenobiotic compounds by optimizing the design and operation of detention ponds. The findings from this study could also lead to improvements in existing detention ponds.

A pilot-scale facility, such as the SUDS facility at AAU, is well-suited for further experiments aimed at enhancing separation efficiency in urban water management. The collaboration between the University of A Coruña (UDC) and Aalborg University (AAU) serves as an example of how pilot-scale demonstrations in larger urban drainage facilities through Co-UDlabs can generate fresh insights and innovations for the benefit of the environment, society, and industry.

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